

In this folder, there are multiple files that are compatible with different programs to aid you in constructing a wind tunnel. First, there are three PDFs showing the relative sizes and shapes of the components used to build the tunnel. There is also an Adobe Illustrator version of this information called "AlpineWindTunnel_component.dimensions." Finally, there are two files called "AlpineWindTunnel_3D.components." One is a ".f3d" file that is compatible with the computer-aided design program, Autodesk Fusion. The other is a 3D object file (.stl) that was generated from the Autodesk Fusion file. This .stl file type is widely used and accepted by 3D printing programs. For questions, please feel free to reach out to Courtenay Ray at cray10@uwyo.edu.